

The logo features a stylized sun with yellow rays and a semi-circle, positioned above a white banner that contains the word "LUMINOSITY" in a multi-colored, sans-serif font. The banner is set against a background of a sunset over water, with a blue and green wave-like shape on the left side.

LUMINOSITY

LARGE AREA UNIFORM INDUSTRY COMPATIBLE PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELL TECHNOLOGY

LUMINOSITY is an industry driven project aimed at leveraging the flexible perovskite solar cells technology to commercially relevant production scales, using established industrial processes.

LUMINOSITY will promote flexible perovskite solar cell technology to commercially relevant production scales using industrially proven roll-to-roll (R2R) processing methods, targeting photovoltaic module power conversion efficiency of >20% at an area of >900 cm², by closing the efficiency gap between lab-scale and fab-scale processed devices, and by bringing TRL up to 7.

The final product is a R2R produced, flexible single-junction perovskite PV module that is processed on an aluminium foil. LUMINOSITY target operational stability exceeding 20 years that rivals the lifetime of current commercial thin film PV technologies, while ensuring economic and environmental feasibility.

WWW.LUMINOSITY-PROJECT.EU

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101147653, project Luminosity